

Investigation of AMN Impedance Uncertainty Contribution in Conducted Emission Tests

Soydan Cakir¹, Osman Sen¹, Alexander Kriz², Serdar Büyük¹, Aykut Ayaydin¹

¹TUBITAK National Metrology Institute (TUBITAK UME), Kocaeli, Turkiye

²EMC and Optics, Seibersdorf Laboratories, 2444 Seibersdorf, Austria

Abstract— The conducted emission test is one of the important EMC tests in the frequency range of 10 kHz – 30 MHz for commercial and military equipment. AMNs are required in order to perform measurements and AMN impedance contributes to measurement uncertainty to some extent. Although AMN impedance is defined in terms of magnitude & phase and its effects are studied in commercial standards, most standards such as military standards only define the magnitude and give no information about the uncertainty contribution.

In this paper, firstly we developed a software solution to calculate the theoretical nominal AMN impedance values for a given AMN circuit and calculated the corresponding uncertainty contribution by using the magnitude & phase information in accordance with CISPR 16-4-2. Following this, we instructively studied a variety of widely used AMN types and performed their uncertainty analysis. Finally, we focused particularly on military tests and the uncertainty contribution of the defined military AMNs to military conducted emission tests where phase information is not defined.

Keywords— AMN, Conducted, CE102, EMC, Emission, LISN, Military, Uncertainty.

I. INTRODUCTION

The conducted emission test is applied to commercial and military equipment by measuring conducted emissions from supply ports of the Equipment Under Test (EUT) often in the frequency range of 10 kHz - 30 MHz in order to determine emission levels of the EUT. The conducted emission test firstly requires a verification process performed with known calibrated signal levels or reference sources just before the test in some standards such as MIL-STD-461G [1] or as per quality systems of accredited laboratories. During the verification, generally a known voltage level is applied to the EUT ports of the Artificial Mains Networks (AMN) and it is checked that whether the system displays expected results. If the deviation between the known voltage level and the measured voltage is higher than ± 3 dB, the system is accounted problematic and it should be rectified before proceeding to the test stage. In the test stage, voltage emissions from the EUT are measured through AMNs and a frequency-selective receiver. Although the EUT is supplied through the AMNs during the test, the AMN impedance deviation from the nominal impedance affects the test results and contributes to measurement uncertainties to some extent.

The specifications of the commercial AMNs are given in CISPR 16-1-2 [2]. There are two prominent types of AMNs defined in CISPR 16-1-2 to cover the frequency range from 9

kHz to 30 MHz; the $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H} + 5 \Omega$ AMN from 9 kHz to 150 kHz and the $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H}$ AMN from 150 kHz to 30 MHz. In CISPR 16-1-2, the tolerance of the impedance is specified. Boundaries are given for the magnitude with $\pm 20 \%$ and for the phase with $\pm 11.5^\circ$ across the whole frequency band. This means that the tolerance is accounted an annulus sector around the nominal impedance as seen in Fig. 1. It is assumed that both boundaries are not independent from each other as per CISPR 16-4-2 [3 - 6]. On the other hand, there seems to have been an ambiguity between the specification in CISPR 16-1-2 and the impact of the tolerance given in CISPR 16-4-2. A rectangular tolerance sector (independently $\pm 20 \%$ for the magnitude and $\pm 11.5^\circ$ for the phase) appears to be defined in CISPR 16-1-2 whereas the calculation of the impact is based on a tolerance circle (dependently $\pm 20 \%$ for the magnitude and $\pm 11.5^\circ$ for the phase as seen in Fig. 1) in CISPR 16-4-2. In fact, this is interpreted in a different manner by some people, also by many calibration laboratories and AMN manufacturers, as follows because of this ambiguity; the annular tolerance in CISPR 16-4-2 is only for defining nominal AMN uncertainty component δZ_{AN} which is used to calculate U_{CISPR} in CISPR 16-4-2 for conducted emission tests. Having an AMN impedance uncertainty value (δZ_{AMN}) larger than δZ_{AN} will only mean a higher uncertainty contribution to the overall expanded test uncertainty but does not mean the AMN cannot be used for testing as long as the CISPR16-1-2 magnitude limits are met. If the CISPR16-1-2 magnitude limits are exceeded, that signifies the AMN cannot be used for testing and must be fixed before placing it in use. Nevertheless, exceeding phase limits is tolerable and it is evaluated in the uncertainty calculation. As a result of all, due to the aforementioned ambiguity, it might be deduced that CISPR 16-1-2 states independent magnitude and phase tolerances for checking the AMN adequacy while CISPR 16-4-2 states dependent and annular magnitude and phase tolerances for particularly defining U_{CISPR} . In the scope of this paper, δZ_{AN} will denote the uncertainty component in CISPR 16-4-2 for U_{CISPR} calculation whereas δZ_{AMN} will denote the uncertainty component that results from an actual AMN used in emission testing.

Although CISPR16-1-2 defines a phase tolerance, MIL-STD-461G defines a $50 \mu\text{H}$ AMN whose impedance is as shown in Fig. 3 along with its circuit diagram in Fig. 6 (a) without phase information and tolerance. In the appendix of MIL-STD-461G, $5 \mu\text{H}$ AMNs are also allowed to facilitate testing for EUTs not able to operate properly with $50 \mu\text{H}$ AMNs. In addition, there is no information or guidance about uncertainty calculation in

MIL-STD-461G. Therefore, in this paper, we firstly developed a piece of software which presents more options and features in comparison to the software solutions in literature. In fact, there is a useful software solution in literature in [6] to calculate the AMN uncertainty contribution but is limited to a number of AMNs and for one frequency at a time. Our developed software allows AMN circuit definition and subsequently calculates nominal impedance magnitude & phase information seen by the EUT along with the nominal AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AN}) which is used for U_{CISPR} calculation and based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2. Additionally, the same software calculates the actual AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) to be directly placed in the uncertainty calculation budget of an actual emission test when impedance magnitude and phase values in an actual AMN calibration report taken from a calibration laboratory are entered into the software. Following this, we performed AMN impedance uncertainty analysis for most commonly used AMN types. Finally, we specially focused on the military conducted emission test called CE102 where a phase tolerance for AMNs is not available and which is very often performed in our laboratory.

Fig. 1. Definition of impedance magnitude and phase tolerances [2-6].

Fig. 2. Disturbance voltage measurement model a) ideal case, b) real case [4].

II. ANALYSIS

In CISPR 16-4-1 [7], a measurement model for the conducted disturbance measurement method is given. The disturbance source is modelled by the disturbance voltage V_{EUT} and the source impedance Z_{EUT} . In case of an ideal setup the voltage V_{NOM} is measured at the nominal impedance of the Z_{NOM} as seen in Fig. 2 (a). Due to tolerances the actual impedance will

deviate from the nominal impedance. In this case the source is terminated with the impedance Z_{AMN} , where the disturbance voltage V_{AMN} is measured as depicted in Fig. 2 (b). The measurement error is defined in a log scale as in (1) [4, 6].

$$\Delta V = 20 \log \left(\left| \frac{V_{AMN}}{V_{NOM}} \right| \right) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. MIL-STD-461G AMN impedance magnitude graph and tolerance [1].

In CISPR 16-4-2 a worst case analysis is performed to get the measurement error. The calculation is based on the work of [8], which uses reflection coefficients normalized to system impedance $Z_o = 50$ as given in (2) to (4) [4, 6];

$$\Gamma_{NOM} = \frac{Z_{NOM} - Z_o}{Z_{NOM} + Z_o} \quad (2)$$

$$\Gamma_{AMN} = \frac{Z_{AMN} - Z_o}{Z_{AMN} + Z_o} \quad (3)$$

$$\Gamma_{EUT} = \frac{Z_{EUT} - Z_o}{Z_{EUT} + Z_o} = \rho \exp(j\varphi) \quad (4)$$

The voltages are derived by using (2) to (4) as given in (5) and (6);

$$V_{NOM} = \frac{Z_{NOM}}{Z_{EUT} + Z_{NOM}} V_{EUT} \quad (5)$$

$$V_{AMN} = \frac{Z_{AMN}}{Z_{EUT} + Z_{AMN}} V_{EUT} \quad (6)$$

The measurement error is calculated using (7);

$$\Delta U = 20 \log \left(\left| \frac{1 + \Gamma_{AMN}}{1 - \Gamma_{AMN} \Gamma_{EUT}} \frac{1 - \Gamma_{NOM} \Gamma_{EUT}}{1 + \Gamma_{NOM}} \right| \right) \quad (7)$$

Due to the impedance specification, Z_{AMN} with a tolerance circle is calculated by (8). It is assumed that the worst case will occur if Z_{AMN} is exactly on this circle and not inside the circle. Consequently, in (4), $\rho = 1$ and $|\Gamma_{EUT}|$ is assumed to be 1 [4, 6].

$$Z_{AMN} = Z_{NOM} + 0.2 |Z_{NOM}| e^{j\theta} \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq \theta < 2\pi \quad (9)$$

All possible combinations of φ and θ were used with 0.5 degrees steps in (4) and (8) in the analysis.

The software window developed in the scope of this study is presented in Fig. 4 (a) along with the most general AMN circuit diagram in Fig. 4 (b) analyzed by the software. As depicted in Fig. 4 (a), the software allows the definition of AMNs in a large scale by entering the required AMN circuit component values on the AMN circuit and subsequently produces nominal AMN impedance (Z_{NOM}) seen from the EUT and based on the entered values. It also accepts the actual AMN impedance magnitude and phase values (Z_{AMN}) taken from a calibration laboratory. At the end, while it produces the AMN impedance nominal values (Z_{NOM}) seen from the EUT as depicted in Fig. 4 (b), it also produces uncertainty contribution δZ_{AMN} for the actual AMN impedance, obtained from a AMN calibration laboratory, along with the nominal AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AN}) which is based on the annular tolerance and used for U_{CISPR} calculation as per CISPR 16-4-2. The software additionally allows adjusting the annular impedance magnitude tolerance, if requested, from the 20 % default value to any desired value for special analyses, and changing the 0.5° default φ and θ step in order to increase and decrease the depth of the analysis.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. (a) Software window for AMN impedance and uncertainty calculation, (b) the most general AMN diagram used in the software.

In the scope of the project, we studied the commonly used AMN types whose circuits are given in Fig. 5 – Fig. 8. The power source symbols Fig. 5 – Fig. 8 should not be confused with the voltage source symbol used in Fig. 2. The voltage source symbol seen in Fig. 2 is the internal disturbance source (V_{EUT}) inside the EUT, whereas the source symbol seen in Fig. 5 – Fig. 8 is the external power source (V_s) (e.g. 220/230 VAC, 50/60 Hz) that supplies the EUT. As seen in Fig. 5 – Fig. 8, depending on the related standard, the AMNs have slight or

significant variations in design and components between them. When we examine the circuitry of the AMNs more carefully, we see that the CISPR 16-1-2 $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H} + 5 \Omega$ & CISPR 16-1-2 $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H}$ combination, MIL-STD-461 $50\mu\text{H}$, ANSI C63.4 [9] AMNs are fundamentally similar apart from some minor components & values. For that reason, we selected the MIL-STD-461G $50\mu\text{H}$ AMN along with CISPR 16-1-2 $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H} + 5 \Omega$ & CISPR 16-1-2 $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H}$ AMN combination for analysis to represent this AMN group. Likewise, the MIL-STD-461G $5 \mu\text{H}$, CISPR 25 [10], and DO-160G [11] AMNs are similar and we selected the MIL-STD-461G $5 \mu\text{H}$ AMN for analysis to represent this second group. However, as ISO 7637-2 [12] and ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C [13] AMNs are markedly different in terms of circuitry and analysis results, we analyzed each of them separately. As a consequence, for each selected AMN type, we calculated nominal impedance magnitude & phase impedance curves and δZ_{AN} stated in CISPR16-4-2 for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the tolerance circle shown in Fig. 1. In this study, regardless of the relevant standards of the studied AMNs, all the AMN types were analyzed in the same configuration with the following parameters for consistency; the short-circuit and open-circuit source impedance conditions, the frequency range of 9 kHz - 400 MHz that reflects the widest AMN frequency range considering most of the AMN-related standards, and annular 20 % magnitude & $\pm 11.5^\circ$ phase tolerance. In fact, the treatment of the source side differs from one standard to another during impedance calibration. For instance, the open-circuit condition is demanded for ANSI C63.4, MIL-STD-461, DO-160G while the short circuit condition is for CISPR 25, ISO 11452-2. Both of the conditions have good arguments; the short-circuit condition may signify the theoretical correct treatment of a voltage source whereas the open-circuit condition may denote that the source side of the AMN is connected to the source with a cable. From an RF perspective the impedance of this cable is high due to the inductance of the cable. Additionally, it is practical in calibration with the open-circuit condition since no additional adapter is required.

Our prominent aim was to show the usability of the software in any desired configuration even different from the configurations stated in the related AMN standards, if required. In addition, independently of the relevant standards of the analysed AMN types & their related frequency ranges, it was aimed to set out the results in the entire frequency range (9 kHz – 400 MHz) per AMN. Therefore, readers can also have the chance of seeing the full picture of the entire range which is not shown in the relevant AMN standards.

Afterwards, we particularly focused on MIL-STD-461G $50 \mu\text{H}$ and $5 \mu\text{H}$ AMNs as they are often utilized in our laboratory in the MIL-STD-461G CE102 test and no phase tolerance is defined for them in the standard. In this context, we applied the uncertainty calculation methodology stated in CISPR 16-4-2 to the military CE102 test for both the open-circuit and short-circuit power source impedance conditions. In this context, we firstly produced nominal impedance values and δZ_{AN} , which is stated in CISPR16-4-2 for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the tolerance circle, for the military AMN by using the developed software. Thereafter, we used one of our actual AMNs and its calibration certificate taken from a calibration laboratory in an

attempt to calculate the actual AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) to be placed into the uncertainty budget of the CE102 test. Although phase information is not stipulated by the standard for military AMNs, we requested the phase information from the calibration laboratory along with the magnitude information particularly for this research. Consequently, the actual AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) was calculated to be used in CE102 uncertainty budget.

Fig. 5. CISPR 16-1-2 ideal AMN diagrams excerpted from the standard (a) $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H} + 5 \Omega$, (b) $50 \Omega / 50 \mu\text{H}$.

Fig. 6. MIL-STD-461G AMN (a) $50 \mu\text{H}$, (b) $5 \mu\text{H}$.

Fig. 7. Automotive test AMNs as per (a) ISO 7637-2, (b) CISPR 25.

Finally, we formed a MIL-STD-461G $50 \mu\text{H}$ AMN simulation with an intentionally and slightly exaggerated phase deviation higher than $\pm 11^\circ$ in order to have an idea of the possible impact

of a significant phase deviation on the AMN uncertainty component. In this simulation, while precisely keeping the AMN impedance magnitude at the nominal impedance magnitude, we intentionally increased the phase deviation by 50° from the nominal phase for the simulated AMN for all frequencies in the software and put it into analysis and evaluated the results. Conversely, we also reduced the CISPR 16-4-2 annular magnitude and phase impedance tolerance from $20\% / 11.5^\circ$ to $1\% / 0.57^\circ$ for the MIL-STD $50 \mu\text{H}$ AMN (R_S : short-circuit) selected just as an example to check the extent of improvement in voltage deviation through the significant tolerance reduction.

III. ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The nominal impedance magnitude and phase values of the most commonly used AMNs, which were calculated by the developed software, are presented in Fig. 9 (a) – Fig. 17 (a). Additionally, δZ_{AN} values based on the annular tolerance in accordance with CISPR 16-4-2 are given in Fig. 9 (b) – Fig. 17 (b) and Table I with the obtained peak values. The second column of Table I shows the maximum and minimum AMN voltage deviations in the range of 9 kHz – 400 MHz which is deemed as the widest AMN frequency range in this research regardless of the AMN’s relevant standards, whereas the third column shows the values particularly in the frequency range stated in the standard where the relevant AMN is defined.

Fig. 8. Other reputable AMN types (a) DO-160G, (b) ANSI C63.4, (c) ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C.

As clearly seen in Fig. 9 (b) and Table I, the MIL-STD-461G 50 μH AMN with the open-circuit source impedance condition stipulated by the standard gives maximum voltage deviations of +3.32 dB / -2.94 dB when the annular tolerance is $\pm 20\%$ for the magnitude and $\pm 11^\circ$ for the phase in accordance with CISPR 16-4-2, which can be accounted reasonable performance in the frequency range of 9 kHz – 400 MHz. Also, the calculated magnitude curve in Fig. 9 (a) is the same as the military standard curve shown in Fig. 3, as expected. On the other hand, its analysis with the short-circuit source impedance condition yields a dramatic change in the impedance phase and voltage deviation as shown in Fig. 10 but it gives an impedance magnitude curve akin to the open-circuit source impedance condition, which means the MIL-STD-461 50 μH AMN requires vigilant use in low-impedance source conditions below 50 kHz and the AMNs employed in CE102 tests should have an impedance tolerance as low as possible in the low frequency range. It shows very clearly how important the specification of the phase is. For the open condition (Fig. 9) the phase is limited to approximately 55° and the voltage deviation is acceptable. For short condition (Fig. 10) the phase comes close to 90° where a resonance occurs and the voltage deviation goes up. When we have a look at Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, it is noticed that the MIL-STD-461 5 μH AMN with both the open-circuit and short-circuit source impedance conditions appears to be not usable in the frequency range of 9 kHz – 1 MHz considering the CISPR 16-4-2 annular tolerance although the standard presents its usable impedance curve as from 150 kHz, on the grounds that some EUTs are not operating properly with 50 μH AMNs. Regarding the CISPR AMNs, the combination of CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω & CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μH AMNs is very usable from 9 kHz as given in Fig. 13 based on the aforementioned annular tolerance and its magnitude & phase results are completely compatible with the standard tables given in CISPR16-1-2. Additionally, the resemblance of the CISPR AMN curves in Fig. 13 to the curves of the MIL-STD-461 AMN (R_s : open-circuit) in Fig. 9 is striking. It should be noted that the CISPR AMNs analyzed in this paper are ideal AMNs in their simplest form as excerpted from the standard (see Fig. 5). Ultimately, ISO 7637-2 and ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMNs show their intrinsic behavior in magnitude, phase and δZ_{AN} curves as seen in Fig. 14 – Fig. 17 for both the short-circuit and open-circuit source impedance conditions. The ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMN seems to show the worst performance and become usable beyond 2 MHz for both of the source impedance conditions as seen in Fig. 16 – Fig. 17 based on the same annular tolerance given in CISPR 16-4-2. Nevertheless, it should be stressed that the ECSS AMN is not intended to measure the disturbance voltage and the disturbance current is measured with a current probe in the standard. Here, an answer is sought to the question “what happens if an ECSS AMN is used in conducted emission

tests?”. As a result, it looks that the ECSS AMN is not suitable at all for the use in conducted emission tests considering the CISPR 16-4-2 tolerances. When we examine the ISO 7637-2 AMN results in Fig. 14 – Fig. 15, we see at the first glance that there is significant difference between the short-circuit and open-circuit source impedance condition results. The impedance magnitude curve for the open-circuit source impedance is utterly incompatible with the curve given in the standard whereas there is good agreement with the standard for the short-circuit power source case as the ISO 7637-2 requires the source side is short-circuited in calibration. However, the voltage deviation is remarkably high below 1 MHz for the short-circuit source impedance condition while the severity of the deviation is alleviated for the open-circuit source impedance condition and seems to be usable beyond 50 kHz in terms of voltage deviation. In fact, for ISO 7637-2 the magnitude tolerance is only 10 %, but the 20 % / 11.5° annular tolerance from CISPR is implemented here in this paper just for information and for making it comparable to the other analysed AMNs. When the overall results are evaluated together, the best performance is shown by the ANSI C63.4 AMN independently of source impedance conditions in the entire frequency range in accordance with Table I based on the annular tolerance of CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 9. MIL-STD-461 50 μH AMN (R_s : Open) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} based on the annular tolerance for U_{CISPR} calculation as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 10. MIL-STD-461 50 μH AMN (R_s : Short) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} based on the annular tolerance for U_{CISPR} calculation as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 11. MIL-STD-461 5 μH AMN (R_S : open-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} based on the annular tolerance for U_{CISPR} calculation as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 12. MIL-STD-461 5 μH AMN (R_S : short-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} based on the annular tolerance for U_{CISPR} calculation as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 13. Combination of CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω (9 kHz – 150 kHz) & CISPR 16-1-2 50 Ω / 50 μH (150 kHz – 400 MHz) AMNs (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 14. ISO 7637-2 AMN (R_S : open-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 15. ISO 7637-2 AMN (R_S : short-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 16. ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMN (R_S : open-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Fig. 17. ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C AMN (R_S : short-circuit) (a) nominal magnitude and phase information, (b) maximum and minimum deviation δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2.

Table I. Nominal AMN uncertainty component δZ_{AN} for U_{CISPR} calculation by AMN types based on the annular tolerance as per CISPR 16-4-2 in the range of 9 kHz – 400 MHz and specifically in the relevant AMN standard ranges.

AMN Type	CISPR 16-4-2 δZ_{AN} (dB) (9 kHz – 400 MHz)	CISPR 16-4-2 δZ_{AN} (dB) (AMN's standard frequency range)
CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μH + 5 Ω (9 kHz – 150 kHz) & CISPR 50 Ω / 50 μH (150 kHz – 400 MHz)	3.59 / -3.07	3.59 / -3.07 (9 kHz – 30 MHz)
MIL-STD-461 50 μH (R_S : open-circuit)	3.32 / -2.94	3.32 / -2.94 (10 kHz – 10 MHz)
MIL-STD-461 50 μH (R_S : short-circuit)	42.18 / -20.06	42.18 / -20.06 (10 kHz – 10 MHz)
MIL-STD-461 5 μH (R_S : open-circuit)	45.53 / -20.80	45.53 / -12.31 (150 kHz – 30 MHz)
MIL-STD-461 5 μH (R_S : short-circuit)	44.29 / -18.78	42.82 / -10.62 (150 kHz – 30 MHz)
ISO 7637-2 (R_S : open-circuit)	11.31 / -5.24	1.70 / -2.01 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
ISO 7637-2 (R_S : short-circuit)	53.07 / -18.76	53.07 / -13.53 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
CISPR 25 (R_S : open-circuit)	45.42 / -21.06	45.42 / -16.02 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
CISPR 25 (R_S : short-circuit)	49.99 / -18.89	41.48 / -13.31 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
DO-160G (R_S : open-circuit)	46.35 / -26.02	46.35 / -26.02 (10 kHz – 400 MHz)
DO-160G (R_S : short-circuit)	49.99 / -18.89	49.99 / -18.89

(R _S : short-circuit)		(10 kHz – 400 MHz)
ANSI C63.4 (R _S : open-circuit)	3.33 / -2.94	3.33 / -2.94 (9 kHz – 30 MHz)
ANSI C63.4 (R _S : short-circuit)	3.31 / -2.93	3.31 / -2.93 (9 kHz – 30 MHz)
ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C (R _S : open-circuit)	49.87 / -12.29	49.87 / -10.33 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)
ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-07C (R _S : short-circuit)	48.15 / -10.88	48.15 / -10.88 (100 kHz – 100 MHz)

Besides, although the voltage deviations seem to be very high and unacceptable in both the two and third columns of Table I for some AMNs, this should be reiterated here that all the analysis in Table I is based on the 20 % / 11.5° annular tolerance of CISPR16-4-2 irrelevant of the related standards of the analyzed AMNs, which means that the uncertainty contribution arising from these AMNs can be reduced by choosing AMNs with a lower impedance tolerance for conducted emission tests. When a calibration report for an AMN is received from a calibration laboratory, it can be checked through the developed software. However, as studied above, the way of the AMN source side termination could have a significant effect on the AMN impedance, especially in the low frequency range and users should be cautious about it.

The actual calibration data of our selected military 50μH and 5μH AMNs obtained from a calibration laboratory in the range of 10 kHz – 30 MHz is given in Fig. 18 (a) – Fig. 19 (a). As we already know the nominal impedance magnitude & phase information from Fig. 9 (a) and 11 (a) for the open-circuit source impedance condition, the actual AMN uncertainty components are easily produced in the entire CE102 test frequency range 10 kHz – 10 MHz as given in Fig. 18 (b) – Fig. 19 (b) and Table II to be directly used in the CE102 uncertainty budget table. As our military AMNs were calibrated by the calibration laboratory up to 30 MHz beyond the CE102 standard frequency range, we also extended the frequency range in the graphs to 30 MHz for further information. As it is clearly seen in Fig. 19 (b), we should be very careful while using the 5 μH AMN in CE102 tests as uncertainty contribution is severe in the range of 10 kHz – 300 kHz whereas the 50 μH AMN contribution presented in Fig.18 (b) is fairly low almost in the full frequency range and it is even less than the δZ_{AN} of U_{CISPR} given in Fig. 9 (b).

Fig. 18. Results of our military 50 μH AMN (R_S : open-circuit) (a) actual magnitude and phase information from a calibration laboratory, (b) actual uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) based on the actual AMN calibration data to be used in military CE102 uncertainty budget.

Fig. 19. Results of our military 5 μH AMN (R_S : open-circuit) (a) actual magnitude and phase information from a calibration laboratory, (b) actual uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) based on the actual AMN calibration data to be used in military CE102 uncertainty budget.

Table II. Summary of military AMN Results in the range of 10 kHz – 30 MHz

AMN Type	Actual Uncertainty Component for Military CE102 Testing δZ_{AMN} (dB) (10 kHz – 30 MHz)
MIL-STD-461G 50 μH	1.14 / -1.5
MIL-STD-461G 5 μH	24.63 / -30.48

Fig. 20. (a) Uncertainty component (δZ_{AMN}) of the AMN simulation with phase information increased by 50°. (b) re-analysis of MIL-STD-461 50 μH AMN (R_S : short-circuit) for voltage deviation with 1 % / 0.57° annular impedance tolerance.

Ultimately, the results of the case where the phase deviation is intentionally increased by 50° in a military 50 μH AMN simulation are given in Fig. 20 (a). It is observed in Fig. 20 that significant deviation in the phase leads to unacceptable and intolerable voltage deviation, which is already explained in CISPR 16-1-2 Annex I. For that reason, the phase requirement should be also integrated into future MIL-STD-461 versions to prevent the situation from going unchecked. Lastly, Fig. 20 (b) shows the improvement in the voltage deviation by means of the reduction in the annular impedance tolerance. When Fig.10 (b) and Fig. 20 (b) are compared, a marked improvement is noticed in the low frequency range, which underlines the importance of having an annular impedance tolerance as low as possible for a military AMN especially in the frequency range close to 10 kHz. The software developed in the scope of the research is downloadable through the link given in [14].

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we developed and introduced a user-friendly and useful software solution which will allow laboratories to calculate their own AMN uncertainty contribution (δZ_{AMN}) for any desired AMN type based on its actual LISN calibration

certificate and we have made it downloadable. The software also can calculate the nominal AMN uncertainty component (δZ_{AN}) which is used to calculate U_{CISPR} as per CISPR 16-4-2 for any AMN type for a standard annular tolerance or a customized one. The analysis made by using the developed software clearly demonstrated how essential the specification of the phase is and consequently all conducted emission related standards which use AMNs such as MIL-STD 461 should specify a phase tolerance to avoid going unchecked in terms of measurement uncertainty. Even this definition should be frequency-dependent as much as possible because much lower tolerance might be required in low frequencies for a suppressed uncertainty contribution. Ultimately, it was shown that both of the ways of the AMN source side termination, namely the open and short circuit conditions, should be particularly defined for the LISN impedance as significant difference might occur between them as reported in this paper and users should be aware of the risks even if the related standards define the impedance and/or phase requirements only for one of them.

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